

**THE ROLE OF EXTRACURRICULAR WORKS ON A FOREIGN
LANGUAGE TEACHING**

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ABSTRACT

At the present stage of the development of education, the humanistic approach prevails in the teaching methodology. The student is at the center of the pedagogical process. To enhance learners' capacities to achieve their learning goals, extra-curricular activities play a crucial role in education in particular in learning foreign languages. This paper attempts to describe productive sides of the activities.

Keywords. Extra-curricular activities, student, teacher, foreign language.

INTRODUCTION

It is vital that, extracurricular work in combination with regular activities opens up wide opportunities for the implementation of humanistic education and the formation of students' worldview through the assimilation of language as an element of national culture and a means of communication. Where extracurricular activities act as a natural continuation of the system of lessons, a genuine pedagogical environment of relaxed communication is created. The preparation and conduct of extracurricular activities (quizzes, contests, matinees, thematic evenings, etc.) helps to increase students' interest in learning a foreign language, improve the quality of knowledge, develop conversational skills, repeat and consolidate previously learned word and expressions, expand vocabulary. Such work poses not only educational, but also educational tasks; students get acquainted with the traditions, customs and culture of another nation, its literary heritage. Extracurricular activities are also important when teaching a foreign language, as well as work in the classroom.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

The main differences between extracurricular and academic work are:

1. The voluntary nature of students' participation in extracurricular activities, as opposed to the mandatory nature of educational activities.
2. The extracurricular nature of classes, which is expressed in the absence of strictly scheduled

regulations concerning the time, place, form of their conduct and in the absence of strict accounting of knowledge, skills and abilities, grades in points. 3. Great independence and initiative of students in performing extracurricular assignments. The preparation and conduct of extracurricular activities increases the interest of students in learning the language by developing internal motivation by transferring the center of the learning process from the teacher to the student.

Extracurricular work is based on the following principles:

1) The principle of the connection of learning with life. The implementation of this principle makes it possible to ensure a close connection of extracurricular work in a foreign language with the living conditions and activities of the student.

2) The principle of students' communicative activity. A prerequisite for higher communicative activity of students in extracurricular activities is the opportunity to choose the most interesting and accessible type of activity: correspondence with foreign friends, reading books in the language being studied.

3) The principle of taking into account the level of language readiness of students and the continuity of extracurricular work with foreign language lessons. In extracurricular work, as well as in the classroom, it is necessary to achieve the conscious application of knowledge, skills and abilities. The formation of students' interest in foreign language activities largely depends on the understanding of the content of the material used, the willingness of students to include it in speech activity.

4) The principle of taking into account the age characteristics of students.

5) The principle of combining collective, group and individual forms of work. A skillful combination of collective, group and individual forms of work is based on the teacher's good knowledge of the contingent of students, their interests, opportunities, plans.

6) The principle of interdisciplinary connections in the preparation and conduct of extracurricular work in a foreign language. The significance of this principle is due, firstly, to the unity of the ultimate goal of the entire educational process – the formation of a comprehensively developed, harmonious personality, and secondly, to the unity of the spiritual essence of a person who cannot be brought up and taught in parts. The effectiveness and efficiency of extracurricular work depends both on taking into account the above principles and on compliance with the following

- voluntary participation;-the combination of student initiative with the guiding role of the teacher;
- entertaining and novelty of the content, forms and methods of work;
- aesthetics of all events held;
- clear organization and thorough preparation of all planned events;
- availability of targets and business prospects;
- wide use of methods of pedagogical stimulation of students' activity;
- publicity.The objectives of extracurricular work in a foreign language are:
 - expansion and deepening of knowledge, skills and abilities in mastering foreign language communication activities;
 - stimulating students' interest in studying the subject;
 - comprehensive personal development, including intellectual, emotionalvolitional and spiritual-moral spheres.

In the methodological literature and in practice, there are usually three forms of extracurricular work: personal, group and mass. The basis of such distribution is assigned a sign of quantitative coverage of participants. Mass forms of extracurricular work do not have a clear organizational structure. These include such events as international clubs, festivals, contests, Olympiads, theme nights, etc. These events are held sporadically. It is advisable that mass events be based on the widespread use of amateur and creative activity of students. In order for these events to become truly massive, it is necessary to widely notify students and thorough preparation. The group form of extracurricular work has a clear organizational structure and a relatively permanent composition of participants united by common interests. Various circles belong to this form: conversational, vocal, dramatic, translators, philatelists, extracurricular reading, etc. Some methodologists recommend organizing conversational and choral circles for all students. Combined circles have proven themselves positively, where different types of activities are combined, for example, learning songs and preparing dramatizations, extracurricular reading and watching movies with further discussion of what has been viewed. Classes in circles are usually held regularly. Circle classes should be based on strictly voluntary principles; circles should be few (12-15 members), since it is more difficult to develop conversational skills in a large audience. Individual extracurricular work is carried out with individual students who prepare a message or report about the country whose language is being studied, about significant dates and events, outstanding people, learn poems, songs, excerpts from literary works in a foreign language, produce visual aids, design wall newspapers, albums, stands, etc. Individual work can be carried

out continuously or sporadically. Individual forms of work represent a mandatory preparatory stage for mass and circle work.

DISCUSSION

Let's note those types of motivation, the development of which contributes to improving the effectiveness of teaching a foreign language:

- 1) target communicative motivation, when the main internal setting is communication with peers and adults;
- 2) inventory motivation resulting from the awareness of the progress achieved by the student in language learning;
- 3) country-specific motivation arising from the satisfaction of a student's specific, emotional and personal interest in the country of the language being studied, its culture, people;
- 4) linguistic-cognitive motivation arising from interest in the language form itself (for example, etymology, vocabulary increment, working with context);
- 5) compensatory motivation - striving for consistency, completeness, nonfragmentarity of acquired knowledge, skills, skills;
- 6) instrumental motivation, which develops on the basis of a sense of joy and satisfaction from performing certain types of work;
- 7) aesthetic motivation resulting from aesthetic pleasure, enjoyment derived from the process of learning a foreign language, from participation in various forms of extracurricular activities. Extracurricular work is an important link in teaching language and culture, promotes the active participation of students in mastering knowledge, forming their ability to independently productive activities in a foreign language. The teacher, in turn, is not only a carrier of knowledge, but also a bright and interesting person who not only transmits knowledge, but also together with students takes part "small discoveries", organizes their educational work in an exciting and interesting way. Next, I would like to describe my own experience of participating in extracurricular activities. Mass extracurricular activities have become widespread in our practice. One of the most difficult tasks facing the teacher in this case is the task of maintaining a high level of motivation of the student when organizing such events. For our independent work, we were offered to read authentic texts, in particular, the works of F.S Fitzgerald "The Great Gatsby". Naturally, we did not read the entire work in its entirety, but excerpts reflecting the main content of the novel. After reading the book, together with the teacher, we compiled questions, assignments, presentations on the material we read.

RESULTS

As a result, the completion of our work on the work was a detailed analysis of it and the decision to hold an extracurricular event of a mass nature in the form of a literary cafe. To organize this event, we have compiled a detailed scenario, tried to recreate the atmosphere of the last century by creating costumes characteristic of that era. Everyone present at our cafe was offered a summary of the work of F.S. Fitzgerald "The Great Gatsby". We talked about the biography of the author, about the creation of this great novel by him, and also watched excerpts from the film "The Great Gatsby" in English, compared the contents of the film and the book and compared them. It should be noted that we all approached the creation and holding of this event with great pleasure and creative enthusiasm - quite a large number of tasks were created, questions were drawn up, presentations were prepared, scenes from the work were played. During our event, we tried to immerse everyone present in the "Jazz Era", as a result of which, we can safely say that this goal was achieved.

CONCLUSION

So, in the process of preparing and conducting our extracurricular work, its main goals were achieved: the development of communication skills, increasing interest in learning the language, the culture of the countries of the studied language, expanding vocabulary, developing the skills to conduct a discussion as well as the ability to work in a group. We managed to organically and creatively approach the organization of our joint work with the teacher. The indisputable advantage of extracurricular work is the fact that both strong and weak in language students get the opportunity to self-actualize in the creative process of preparing and holding events, to feel themselves in a situation of success. The atmosphere of cooperation and creativity has a positive impact on the relationship between the teacher and students. We can safely say that thanks to extracurricular work in a foreign language, the cognitive interests of students are deepened, the development of personality, especially its creative potential, is stimulated, horizons, erudition and emotional value attitude to the world and to oneself are significantly expanded. In other words, extracurricular work in a foreign language contributes to a more effective assimilation of the content of education. This allows us to conclude that the development and implementation of extracurricular activities are necessary to increase the level of motivation to learn a foreign language.

References:

1. Milrud R.P. Methodology and development of methods of teaching foreign languages// Foreign languages at school. – 2005. – № 5.

2. New pedagogical and information technologies in the education system / Ed. by E. S. Polak, M., 2009.
3. Rogova, G. V., Rabinovich, F. M., Sakharov I.e. Methods of teaching
4. Raxmatullayevna, A. D. (2023). INGLIZ TILI DARSLARIDA TARJIMA METODLARINING QO'LLANILISHI. Ustozlar uchun, 17(1), 151-163.
5. Raxmatullayevna, A. D. (2023). CHET TILINI O'QITISHDA TARJIMA METODLARI VA ULARNING TASNIFI. Ustozlar uchun, 17(1), 142-150.
6. Raxmatullayevna, A. D. (2022). USING INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING TRANSLATION. International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research, 633-635. foreign languages in high school. – M., Education, 1990.
7. Smirnov A. N., Fadeev E. A. non-traditional forms of organization of extracurricular activities – SPb.: OOO "Book House", 2011.
8. The formation of interest in teaching pupils [Text] /Edited by A.K. Markova. - M., 2006

